

OPTICAL AND ELECTRICAL STUDIES OF NOVEL FERROELECTRIC COMPOSITES FOR USE IN PHASED ARRAY ANTENNAS

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Abstract- Ceramic composites of barium strontium titanate and other non-ferroelectric oxides have been fabricated for use in phased array antennas. These composites have shown superior electronic properties at low and microwave frequencies in that they have reduced dielectric constants, low loss tangents and high tunabilities. However, minimal work (other than x-ray powder diffraction) has been reported on the correlation of these electronic properties to the site substitutions and the sample topography. Raman and FTIR spectroscopy has been used to study the structural properties related to the additions of both strontium to the barium titanate crystal structure as well as the effect of the additions of oxide III on $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ($1-x = 0.00, 0.15, 0.30, 0.40, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.6, 0.7, 0.80, \text{ and } 1.0$). The optical properties of the ceramic composites have been correlated to the electrical properties of the materials such as the Curie temperatures and these results will be discussed in detail.

I. INTRODUCTION

Phased array antennas can steer transmitted or received signals either linearly or in two dimensions without mechanically oscillating the antenna. In order to make these devices available for many other commercial and military uses, the basic concept of the antenna must be improved. If ferroelectric materials could be used for the phase shifting element instead of ferrites, phased array antennas would be totally revolutionized.

A ceramic Barium Strontium Titanate, $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$, (BSTO), phase shifter using a planar microstrip construction has been demonstrated at 5-10 GHz. [1,2] BSTO/Oxide III (designated as oxide III as the materials are undergoing the patent filing process) composites have shown greatly improved electronic properties at both low (KHz-MHz) to microwave frequency regions (10 GHz).[3] Most notably the loss tangents have been reduced to less than 0.002.[4] However, in order to improve the already adequate performance of the antennas, we have investigated composites with even lower loss tangents. We have therefore fabricated $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ (BSTO) ceramics with a various molar ratios of barium, including, $1-x = 0.00, 0.30, 0.40, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, 0.70, \text{ and } 1.00$. The electronic properties of all of the above named compositions were then examined. Additionally, Fourier transform Raman and infrared spectroscopy was utilized to characterize the BSTO composite as a function of the Ba / ratio and the site substitution of oxide III. Subsequently it was found that the materials containing barium content, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55 and

0.60 were the most promising in terms of the electronic properties appropriate for use in phased array antennas. Therefore, composites of $Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.50}Sr_{0.50}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO_3$, and $Ba_{0.60}Sr_{0.40}TiO_3$ /Oxide III were fabricated and the electrical properties and optical properties were obtained.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Ceramic Processing

Powder forms of Barium Titanate and Strontium Titanate were obtained from Ferro Corporation, Transelco Division, Pen Yan, N.Y. (product nos. 219-6 and 218 respectively), stoichiometrically mixed to achieve $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ($1-x = 0.15, 0.30, 0.40, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, 0.70, 0.80 \text{ and } 1.00$) and ball-milled in ethanol using 3/16" alumina media for 24 hrs. The resulting BSTO was then air-dried, calcined at $1100^{\circ}C$ and specimens containing ($1-x = 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, \text{ and } 0.60$) were mixed with a non-ferroelectric oxide (oxide III) at 1.0, 5.0, 10.0, 20.0, 30.0., and 60.0 wt% and ball-milled again in a slurry of ethanol using the alumina grinding media for an additional 24 hrs.

An aqueous based binder was added, Rholpex B-60A (Rohm and Haas Co., Philadelphia, PA) to the resulting BSTO-Oxide mixtures. The mixtures were then air-dried and dry-pressed uniaxially to a pressure of approximately 7000 p.s.i.. Sintering schedules were obtained by employing a deflectometer such as Mitutoyo digimatic indicator and miniprocessor (Mitutoyo Corp., Paramus N.J.). It should be noted that all of the examined samples have % liquid absorption of less than 2%.

Metallization of the ceramics was accomplished by screen printing on electrodes with a silver based ink, Ferro Product #T2026. The specimens were refired at $760^{\circ}C$.

B. Electronic Measurements

The dielectric constants, ϵ' , loss, $\tan \delta$, % tunability were determined for all composites before application of high voltages. The % tunability of a material is determined using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ tunability} = \{ \epsilon' (0) - \epsilon' (V_{app}) \} / \{ \epsilon' (0) \} \quad (1)$$

The tunability measurements were taken with an applied electric field which ranged from 0 to 2.0 V/ μm . The

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electronic properties given in the tables were measured at a frequency of 1 KHz. Capacitance measurements for all materials were taken using an HP4284A LCR meter. Further calculations were done to correct for the effect of fringe capacitance.

C. Optical Measurements

The optical measurements include both Fourier transform Raman (FT-Raman) and infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The FT-Raman spectra were obtained using a Nicolet 950 spectrometer. The system uses a 180° reflective backscattering geometry, a solid state Nd:YVO₄ excitation laser, and an InGaAs detector. An average of 50-128 scans for each spectra were taken. The FTIR spectra were obtained using a Nicolet 750 spectrometer. The spectra were taken with a diffuse reflectance attachment in the mid infrared region (400 to 4000 cm⁻¹) using a KBr beam splitter and a DTGS detector. An average of 32 scans for each spectra were taken. Since polycrystalline ceramic specimens were used in this study no selective polarization was applied for acquisition of either FT-Raman or FTIR spectra.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Electronic Properties

The electronic properties of the BSTO ceramics (1-x = 0.00, 0.30, 0.40, 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, 0.70, and 1.00) are shown in Table I. It is evident from the table that the materials with 1-x = 0.00, 0.30, and 0.40 do not possess sufficient tunability (< 10%) even without the addition of the oxide additive. Since the addition of the additive would further reduce the tunability, these compositions are eliminated. On the other hand, the specimens with 1-x = 0.70 and 1.00 possess loss tangents which are too high (even the addition of the additive could not sufficiently reduce the loss). However, the specimens with 1-x = 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60 seem to possess the appropriate dielectric constants, loss tangents, and tunabilities to be then fabricated into BSTO/Oxide III composites.

The electronic properties of the BSTO-Oxide III composite ceramics are listed in Table II. All of the BSTO / Oxide III composites exhibit reduced dielectric constants and loss tangents. As shown in the table, these properties can be reduced further by lowering the barium content. The dielectric constants of the Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO₃, Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO₃, Ba_{0.50}Sr_{0.50}TiO₃, Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO₃ / Oxide III composite specimens are the most different at lower weight percent oxide III, decreasing with lower barium content, as would be expected from the differences in the Curie temperatures (see Table II). The resulting materials become more "paraelectric" and the values of the loss tangents are reduced with decrease in barium content.

However, the tunability of the materials is also decreased with decreasing barium content. Again, this is in agreement with the position of the Curie temperatures. For example if one compares the Curie temperature undoped of Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO₃, 10°C, and Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO₃, -45°C, it is obvious that the materials with lower barium content have much lower Curie temperatures, i.e., are more "paraelectric" at room temperature and more closely resemble the electrical behavior of a linear capacitor and therefore have less tunability. Since the values for the dielectric constants, loss tangents, and the tunabilities of the undoped specimens are much greater, in order to accentuate the data for BSTO/Oxide III composites, we have excluded the data for undoped specimens from Figs 1-3.

As shown in Fig. 1, it is evident that the tunability of the materials increases linearly with increasing field strength and the application of even higher electric fields is currently being investigated. It is apparent from the electronic data that the Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO₃ and Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO₃ / Oxide III composites provide the best combination of reduced dielectric constants, loss tangents, and maintenance of usable tunabilities.

Table I. Electronic properties of Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO₃, bulk ceramics, measured at 1 KHz,

Barium Content	Dielectric Constant	Loss Tangent	Tunability (2.0 μm)	Curie Temp (°C)
0.00	349.04	0.00022	0.000	-240
0.30	760.04	0.00025	2.200	-105
0.40	1199.12	0.00030	7.900	-65
0.45	1280.83	0.01184	15.20	-45
0.50	1907.99	0.05538	25.55	-25
0.55	2771.73	0.03904	33.40	-15
0.60	5160.64	0.00961	56.30	10
0.70	4322.86	0.03355	48.60	40
1.00	2082.38	0.03675	18.00	135

Table II. Electronic properties of $Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.50}Sr_{0.50}TiO_3$, and $Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO_3$ / Oxide III composite bulk ceramics, measured at 1 KHz, with an applied electric field of 2.0 V/ μ m.

Barium Content	Oxide Content (wt%)	Dielectric Constant	Loss Tangent	Tunability	Curie Temp ($^{\circ}$ C)
Ba = 0.45	0	1280.83	0.01184	15.20	-45
	10	768.06	0.00068	3.90	-75
	20	418.98	0.00064	2.47	-70
	60	78.81	0.00049	3.67	-95
Ba=0.50	0	1907.99	0.05538	25.55	-25
	10	928.01	0.00076	5.48	-55
	20	592.20	0.00073	6.44	-55
	60	77.52	0.00096	3.66	-95
Ba=0.55	0	2771.73	0.03904	33.40	-15
	10	1114.02	0.00094	8.88	-40
	20	742.29	0.00085	8.77	-40
	60	94.59	0.00034	6.46	-50
Ba=0.60	0	5160.64	0.00961	56.30	10
	10	1527.34	0.00162	16.60	-30
	20	1068.43	0.00194	15.80	-35
	60	116.86	0.00148	9.99	-55

Figure 1. Percent tunability versus applied field (V/ μ m) of $Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.50}Sr_{0.50}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO_3$ / 60 wt% oxide III composites, (lines are drawn to aid the eye).

C. Fourier Transform Raman and Infrared Spectroscopy

The FT-Raman spectra for the $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ceramics are shown in Fig. 2. As shown in the figure, there are several sharp lower frequency modes (from ~ 110 to ~ 725 cm^{-1}) associated with $BaTiO_3$ and these have been compared to those found in the literature.[5-7] In particular the 515 cm^{-1} mode associated with the Ti-O stretching mode in $BaTiO_3$ shifts downward in frequency as barium is added, as would be expected upon the addition of a heavier atom. On the hand, there is a broad mode around 1576 cm^{-1} and a smaller sharper mode at 2960 cm^{-1} associated with $SrTiO_3$ (also evident for $Ba_{0.15}Sr_{0.85}TiO_3$). As shown in the inset of Fig. 2, it is evident that increases in the barium content in BSTO causes a systematic shift upward in frequency in the broad 1576 cm^{-1} line associated with $SrTiO_3$. This shift can be related to the shift in the Curie temperature and to the changes in the crystal structure. Further temperature dependent Raman studies to quantify this relationship are currently underway.

The FTIR spectra for the $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ceramics are shown in Fig 3(a), 3(b) and 3(c). These frequency regions have been plotted separately to clarify the shift in the corresponding infrared modes. There are three infrared active modes, $472-483$ cm^{-1} , $784-858$ cm^{-1} , and $1252-1326$ cm^{-1} . The mode from $472-483$ cm^{-1} is the transverse optical modes associated with $BaTiO_3$ (observed at 472 cm^{-1}), $SrTiO_3$ (observed at 483 cm^{-1}) and are also a Raman allowed mode. The $784-858$ cm^{-1} is the longitudinal optical modes also associated with $BaTiO_3/SrTiO_3$ and are Raman allowed modes which were observed in Figure 2. The modes at $1252-1326$ cm^{-1} which appears to be combination of both longitudinal and transverse optical modes active in both the Raman and infrared regions. All of these modes shift downward in frequency as barium is added to the lattice.

Figure 2. FT-Raman spectra of $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ceramics, ($1-x = 0.00, 0.15, 0.30, 0.40, 0.50, 0.60, 0.70, 0.80$ and 1.00). The inset shows the Raman shift versus barium content of $SrTiO_3$ mode.

Figure 3(a)-3(c) FTIR spectra of $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ceramics, ($1-x = 0.00, 0.15, 0.30, 0.40, 0.50, 0.60, 0.70, 0.80$ and 1.00).

This would be expected as barium is substituted into the lattice for the much lighter strontium atoms, the force constant is decreased and therefore the frequency of vibration goes down. Again as in the case of the FT-Raman spectra the shift in frequency versus barium content for the three modes described above is nearly linear and again can be related to the shift in the Curie temperatures shown in Table I.

The FT-Raman spectra for the $Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO_3$ / Oxide III composite specimens are shown in Fig. 4. These spectra shown in Fig 4 are typical of all $Ba_{1-x}Sr_xTiO_3$ ceramics / oxide III composites and have therefore been used here as representative of $Ba_{0.55}Sr_{0.45}TiO_3$, $Ba_{0.50}Sr_{0.50}TiO_3$, and $Ba_{0.45}Sr_{0.55}TiO_3$ / oxide III composites. It should be noted that for additions of oxide III < 1.0 wt%, the 2300 cm^{-1} mode of the undoped $Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO_3$ ceramic, shifts upward in frequency. However, as the oxide content is increased from 1.0 wt %, the mode is shifted downward to around 1910 cm^{-1} (the position of the Raman mode associated with the oxide III additive) and the lower frequency modes associated with $BaTiO_3$ are dampened. As shown in the inset of Fig. 4, the peak position of the $1567\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ mode associated with either $SrTiO_3$ or Oxide III is independent of barium content; the addition of oxide III above 1.0 wt% does not appear to substitute into the BSTO lattice. This conclusion agrees the x-ray results for the BSTO-Oxide III composites which shows peaks corresponding to oxide III even with only a 1 wt% addition. Also, as was shown in Table II, the position of the Curie temperature for all BSTO / Oxide III composites is approximately unchanged from 1- 30 wt% oxide III additions. Again, this would indicate that the additive is no longer substituting into the BSTO lattice.

The position of the all three infrared modes ($\sim 479, 825,$ and 1273 cm^{-1}) found in the FTIR spectra of the $Ba_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}TiO_3$

Figure 4. FT-Raman spectra of $\text{Ba}_{0.60}\text{Sr}_{0.40}\text{TiO}_3$ / Oxide III composites. Inset shows the Raman shift versus oxide III content of the BSTO / Oxide III composites for the SrTiO_3 / Oxide III mode.

/ Oxide III are relatively unaffected by the addition of oxide III up to 60 wt% additive. At 60 wt% oxide III addition, the modes at $479, 825 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shift upward in frequency. This may be related to the fact the oxide III atoms are much lighter than those of Ba, Sr. The 479 cm^{-1} becomes dampened (as evidenced in the linear increase in the line broadening of the mode) as the oxide III content was increased and is completely dampened at 60 wt% additive. This may due to the superposition of the oxide III infrared mode which has a corresponding frequency of $\sim 640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the stress induced in the lattice by the addition of the oxide. The FTIR mode at 1273 cm^{-1} is left unchanged even at 60 wt% additive.

III. CONCLUSIONS

$\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{TiO}_3$ ceramics have been fabricated and optically and electronically characterized. A systematic shift in the FT-Raman spectra was observed in the SrTiO_3 mode and also in the FTIR spectra for modes associated with BaTiO_3 / SrTiO_3 as the barium content was increased. The electronic data indicated that the samples containing $1-x = 0.45, 0.50, 0.55,$ and 0.60 were the best candidates for use in phased array antennas and therefore were fabricated into BSTO / Oxide III ceramic composites. FT-Raman results indicate that after 1 wt% oxide III, the dopant no longer substitutes into the lattice. Also the additive did not show much of an effect on the FTIR modes with the exception of dampening of the 479 cm^{-1} transverse mode as oxide III content was increased. It has been shown that the loss tangent of the composites can be further reduced, with the subsequent decrease in the tunability, as the barium is decreased. Yet, the BSTO (0.55) / Oxide III composites have adequate tunability with lower loss tangents than the BSTO (0.6) / Oxide III composites.

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